

BETWEEN EARTH AND SKY

EXPLORING THE COMPLEX MOTIVATION FOR MEGALITHIC CONSTRUCTION

A STUDY OF MALTA

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Abstract

The megalithic structures of Malta have long been the subject of anthropological interest; however, studies concerning their architectural and cultural significance often lack critical analysis. Existing research tends to reinforce prevailing biases, resulting in an incomplete understanding of the complexities surrounding these sites. This study advocates for a comparative analysis with other Neolithic Mediterranean cultures, particularly focusing on astronomical data and its narratives within megalithic contexts. Challenging conventional interpretations, it posits that social organization in ancient Malta stemmed from collaboration rather than hierarchical control, driven by the imperative to manage essential environmental resources, such as flora and water. While Sicily has historically been seen as having a key influence on Maltese Neolithic culture, this research introduces a paradigm shift by examining the effects of south-to-north migration and cultural interactions on Malta's development. The findings emphasize the necessity for a multidisciplinary approach to illuminate the intricate social dynamics and cultural exchanges that have shaped this era.

Keywords: Megalithic structures, Malta, Neolithic migration, archaeological evidence, cultural symbolism, astronomical knowledge

Introduction

Negotiating the past: diverse interpretations of the Maltese Neolithic landscape

Malta's central yet isolated position in the Mediterranean is often linked to its monumental structures (Robb, 2001; Bonanno, 2008) (Figs. 1 and 2). However, the presence of obsidian artifacts (Vella, 2009) suggests the archipelago's active role in maritime trade, challenging isolation as a limiting factor. Based on archaeological evidence like *Stentinel-*

lo-type pottery at *Għar Dalam*¹, dominant theories hypothesize Sicilian migration to Malta around 5000 BCE (Bonanno, 2016). Malta's proximity to Sicily and its agricultural potential may have attracted skilled farmers. However, the emergence of megalithic architecture indicates a more complex process than simple relocation, with diversity in structures, such as *Haġar Qim*'s Globigerina and *Ġgantija*'s Coralline Limestone², reflecting significant societal evolution. It remains unclear whether builders were directly descended from Sicilian migrants or if other factors influenced this development.

A nuanced analysis of Maltese megalithic architecture should not only address migration from Sicily, but also explore the complex interplay of environ-

1 Located in the southern part of Malta near the village of *Birżebbuġa*, is a significant archaeological site featuring a prehistoric cave with anthropic remains that date back to around 5,400 BCE. It is known for its rich deposits of animal remains and artefacts, providing valuable insights into early human habitation and the region's environment.

2 This juxtaposition of materials offers a compelling lens to explore the interplay of technology, culture, and environment in Maltese prehistory (Bonanno Anthony, interview by Raphael Vassallo. *Was Megalithic Malta the lost city of Atlantis? It all boils down to probabilities*. Maltatoday, November 22, 2022, https://www.maltatoday.com.mt/news/interview/119921/megalithic_malta_lost_city_atlantis_anthony_bonanno. It also suggests a changing relationship with the landscape, raising questions about resource availability or adaptation to new construction techniques. The utilization of coralline limestone in *Ġgantija* invites speculation regarding the technological capabilities of its builders. This harder, more durable stone may indicate a sophisticated understanding of their environment and the challenges of working with a material demanding skilled craftsmanship. In contrast, the subsequent preference for globigerina limestone at *Haġar Qim* raises questions about the evolution of architectural styles and communal functions. The softer nature of globigerina limestone facilitates manipulation and suggests a possible shift towards more intricate design elements and aesthetic considerations.

mine how they reflect the material culture's role in shaping social identities and meaning within cultural landscapes. This approach aligns with Cauvin's notion of a symbolic revolution (2000), which argues that societal transformations in the Neolithic were driven by ideological shifts. Additionally, the thematic approach allows comparisons with other Neolithic cultures across the Mediterranean, highlighting Malta's achievements within the broader framework of cultural exchange and shared knowledge systems. It underscores the evolving nature of cultural identity shaped by tradition, collective memory, and the environment.

Using photographic evidence, architectural drawings, and a thorough literature review, this analysis identifies binary oppositions, gaps in existing knowledge, and discrepancies in prior interpretations of celestial alignment, symbolism, and intercultural contact. Interpretations are framed as hypotheses acknowledging alternative perspectives within a fluid historical narrative. The limitations include the interpretive nature of symbol analysis, potential biases in data interpretation, and constraints due to incomplete archaeological data. Despite these, this study aims to illuminate the complex motivations behind megalithic construction, offering insights into ancient builders in Malta and the symbolic expressions that drove societal transformation.

Exploring these inquiries reveals the intricate interplay between logic, intuition, and inherited wisdom, enhancing our understanding of human intellectual and cultural evolution. This perspective challenges conventional approaches, revealing the multifaceted motivations and insights of ancient Maltese builders, and enriching our comprehension of their monumental legacies.

Prioritizing the pillars of planning: form, view, or celestial alignment?

The construction of a megalithic site allows little room for trial and error, as reallocating resources could potentially be detrimental to the project's success. Despite these challenges, the ongoing construction of these structures within a constrained geographical area inhabited by a small population, including vulnerable groups, suggests an effective

modus operandi (Anati, 2022). The alignment of these structures with solstices, equinoxes, and celestial bodies¹ indicates a well-organized approach guided by knowledge of astronomical events, raising questions about the cultural dynamics that facilitated collective ingenuity.

Fig. 3 A representation of a temple façade is engraved on a prominent upright to the left of the central temple of *Mnajdra* (photo from Anati 2022)

Research suggests that climate-related factors, including wind and orientation, played a role in determining site selection. However, the significance of wind becomes debatable if structures were roofed (Fig. 3) unless it served a specific purpose such as creating echoes or providing shelter. Moreover, the orientation of constructions (the majority pointing southwards; Figs. 4 and 5) and the stone relief forming the wall of a chamber at *Ħaġar Qim* (Fig. 6) had to accommodate the layout of the site and the surrounding terrain, as visibility within and between locations was deemed important (Lomsdalen, 2022) Furthermore, the varying celestial alignments observed in different structures, such as *Borġ in-Nadur*, *Tal-Qadi*, and *Ġgantija South*, raise important questions about deliberate alignment and possible ritual importance.

¹ The premise that builders in Malta aligned their structures with celestial events, such as solstices and equinoxes, is well established in archaeological literature. In the case of Malta, Cutajar (1937) conducted initial observations of Maltese sites, and interest in their astronomical significance renewed in the 1980s through the work of Agius and Ventura, building upon Evans' earlier findings (for a full discussion see Barratt, 2022).

Figure 4 *Ġgantija* – The structure’s layout is depicted by directional arrows (photo adapted from Anati, 2022)

Fig. 5 *Mnajdra* – The structure’s layout is depicted by directional arrows (photo adapted from Anati, 2022)

It is reasonable to conclude that Neolithic builders navigated a complex array of variables, including construction timeframes and limited resources (Anati, 2021). Documenting celestial trajectories likely required substantial effort over multiple generations. Nevertheless, such considerations did not mitigate the labor-intensive nature of megalithic construction (although not beyond human capabilities, as evidenced by the circular walled enclosures at Göbekli Tepe, the world’s oldest megalithic site, which flourished millennia before the Maltese temples).

Further investigation into the underexplored variables, particularly within construction contexts, is essential. While this period featured universal symbolic motifs, societies were responsive to seasonal changes that impacted agricultural and ritual practices. Thus, the definition of ‘way of life’ must be tailored to specific local conditions. In this regard, isolation could have been viewed as a manageable challenge rather than a constraint, highlighting the significance of survival strategies and environmental adaptation.

This reflection challenges the portrayal of these societies as strictly hierarchical and specialized (Anati, 2022). The lack of weaponry evidence in Malta hints at a society focused on cooperation, collective survival, and shared knowledge. The relatively modest internal capacities of megalithic structures and the systematic flattening of the areas surrounding them (Anati, 2021) imply that significant gatherings likely occurred outside, marking a separation between sacred spaces and participants. These patterns indicate that rituals likely involved significant community participation, possibly including not just gathering, but also moving around the structure. This activity may have symbolized both life’s cyclical nature and the unity of believers in their worship, highlighting the interconnection between individual spiritual paths and the broader community.

Flexibility in temple design suggests a dynamic belief system that does not exclude multiple coexisting rituals. Barratt et al. (2020) provide evidence of communal gatherings and feasts, indicating that spiritual practices evolved with changing social environments. This adaptability highlights the in-

terplay between societal development and spiritual expression in the builders' society. The absence of elite burial sites in proximity to these locations suggests a lack of exclusive control by a ruling class; instead, whatever happened in and around the structures enhanced community involvement. Over the centuries, the transmission of expertise has been essential for sustaining these intricate systems. This continuity indicates that cooperation and mutual respect prevailed over hierarchical control, thereby reinforcing an egalitarian society.

While parallels with ancient civilizations like Egypt arise, especially regarding monumental projects, it must be emphasized that by the time the pyramids were constructed, Egypt had centralized political structures exerting authority over populations. In contrast, Malta's social organization during the temple period appears to be more decentralized and collaborative. The inclusive nature of rituals and collective monumental efforts indicate a society fundamentally reliant on cooperation rather than forced labor.

Collaboration over hierarchy: the impact of natural resources

From this broader perspective, a state of coalescence may have emerged from shared cultural practices, mutual support systems, and collaborative endeavors existing outside formal governance structures. The society of these builders appears to have been organized around cooperative efforts uniquely shaped by their contextual and environmental factors. Interestingly, if significant visibility across structures was established (Lomsdalen, 2022), it suggests the absence of clan conflicts, further indicating a harmonious coexistence. The absence of evidence of other builders undertaking similar tasks during this period further highlights the distinctiveness of their collaborative approach in response to specific local conditions.

Key environmental factors, particularly flora and water resources (although the latter was discussed in detail in Grima, 2022), have been insufficiently explored in the existing literature, despite their potential significance in facilitating cooperation and providing valuable insights into ancient commu-

Fig. 6 This photograph shows one of the slabs forming a chamber wall at *Hagar Qim*, which is aligned towards the island of Filfla. It is believed that this slab once supported two figures. Filfla is a small, uninhabited island situated approximately 5.6 km (3.5 miles) south of Malta. Given that Africa is located to the south of Europe, the statues would also generally face Africa as they are oriented towards Filfla. If the statues were positioned to face the exterior of the structure, as the current alignment might suggest, this could further bolster the theory that external activities held significant importance. (photo taken by author at *Hagar Qim*)

nities. The utilization of these resources necessitated collective management and knowledge dissemination, thereby shaping social organization and coordination driven by shared responsibilities in the management of these vital resources.

The abundant flora surrounding megalithic structures likely provided immediate indicators of seasonal cycles that are critical for agriculture (Fig.7). Plants could signal optimal planting and harvesting times, suggesting a shift over time toward resource reallocation that favored both agricultural and spiritual functions. For example, *Hagar Qim* is bordered by sea squill (in Maltese *Basal tal-Ghansar*), and within the site, archaeologists uncovered a carved stone pillar depict-

ing a plant in a pot, often interpreted as a generic plant motif. The hypothesis put forward in this study is that it might have represented a squill specimen owing to its significant bulb and association with natural cycles. While the plant may have served medicinal purposes, it has also been revered in subsequent cultures for its connection to fertility cults, drawing parallels to its use in ancient Egyptian and Greek civilizations (and possibly in Malta during the Neolithic).

Fig. 7 An elaborately carved pedestal with reliefs of potted plants on all four sides (photo taken by author at *Haġar Qim*)

Although the *Well of Cyrene* in Libya and the *Well of Santa Cristina* in Sardinia (both famous for the link between water and astronomical events) date later than the Maltese megalith phase, parallels can be drawn between these sites and celestial events (perhaps defining how these observations were carried out). Most Maltese megaliths, including *Haġar Qim*, align with equinoxes and are strategically positioned near water sources, indicating cultural and intellectual interest in aligning human-made spaces with natural phenomena. The

reflection of sunlight off water likely symbolized the rebirth of the Sun, a theme prevalent in many ancient cultures, enhancing the ritual significance of solstices. The incorporation of water features into the narrative, such as cisterns, adds depth to this interpretation and indicates that the natural environment, including water sources, is a significant intentional factor in site design.

For instance, instead of viewing components such as water sources, celestial alignments, and architectural planning as isolated, they should be seen as interconnected elements that shape megalithic site selection and design. Thus, while the extent to which these builders predominantly led agricultural lives remains subject to debate, it is evident that they actively managed flora, grains, water, and animals to support production and sustenance. Activities within these structures likely integrated spiritual dimensions with practical tasks, indicating multifunctional roles as places of worship and repositories for agricultural surpluses (Fig. 8). The integration of spiritual and practical considerations underscores a comprehensive approach to resource management.

Fig. 8 *Haġar Qim* - a small chamber with a seat and table. Anati (2021) proposed that it may have been the seat of an accountant, scribe, or pharmaceutical chemist (photo from Anati, 2021, MLT 86 EA VIII-20).

However, contradictions arise when considering the significance of alignment with the Crux constellation. Barratt (2022) contends that the limited representation of Crux in the material record suggests that it likely served as a navigational aid rather than playing a significant ritual role. Given Malta's Northern Hemisphere location¹, the practical importance of Crux for navigation is questionable. Its visibility may have been limited to specific times of the year, especially from the horizon, casting doubt on its relevance as a navigational guide for journeys between Malta and Sicily only 90 km apart.

Transcending stone: Exploring the interconnection between sacred spaces and the sea.

Grima (2022) posits that symbols carved in relief around the structures' court may represent water and the sea, while those in apses could signify land-based environments (Figs. 9 and 10). This perspective emphasizes the intrinsic connection between these sacred areas and their broader ecological context, illustrating how ancient architects integrated both terrestrial and marine elements into their narratives.

Sea travel, often conducted at night when the

Fig. 9 Motifs depicting the terrestrial domain (quadrupeds at *Tarxien*) as mentioned in Grima (2022) (photo taken from Anati, 2022)

¹ While Lomsdalen (2022) posits that the Southern Cross was visible from Malta circa 3000 BCE, its location in the Southern Hemisphere raises questions regarding its cultural significance for observers in the Northern Hemisphere. This geographical constraint suggests that alternative constellations, such as the False Cross, and prominent celestial bodies like Sirius, may have held greater relevance to ancient navigational practices and cultural narratives. This observation necessitates further investigation into how these societies conceptualized and interpreted their celestial environment.

Fig. 10 Motifs depicting the maritime domain (spirals at *Hal Tarxien*, but other motifs are also found at *Buġibba* and *Ġgantija*) (photo taken from Anati, 2022)

land was obscured, necessitated reliance on stellar navigation (Robb, 2001; Broodbank, 2013; Pimenta, 2014). The reliance on the Crux constellation stems from the fact that Sirius may not have been as distinct as it is today (Cox, 2001). Notably, travelers journeying from Sicily to Malta would face Crux, while those traveling in the opposite direction would have it behind them, as observed by Stoddart et al. (1993). Therefore, the notion that Crux primarily served as a navigational tool for vessels approaching Malta overlooks its potential utility for voyages originating from the island itself. Thus, it is pertinent to consider why a builder on the archipelago would orient structures towards Crux.

Fig. 11 The boat carvings at *Hal Tarxien* (photo taken from Anati, A.F. and Anati, E., 1988)

The emphasis on Sicily as a primary point of reference diminishes when Malta's geographical advantages are recognized. Given Malta's strategic location and the navigational skills of ancient seafarers, it is plausible that trade routes from Tuni-

sia or the Maghreb region were also accessible, thus influencing maritime trade dynamics. If maritime distances are subject to scrutiny and challenge the assertion that navigation during this period was limited or impractical¹, it is imperative to consider the capabilities of inhabitants who constructed large megalithic structures. Their architectural expertise suggests an advanced understanding of construction materials and techniques, raising questions about the assumption that they were incapable of creating durable vessels suitable for extended voyages.

Furthermore, if commercial interactions occurred, it would be reasonable to hypothesize that the cultural identity of Malta would have influenced neighboring regions, including Sicily. However, despite assertions of significant trade relations that typically facilitate cultural exchange and parallels in architectural practices, megalithic constructions are notably absent in Sicily. The absence of comparable megalithic constructions in Sicily enhances the importance of investigating whether these exchanges were primarily commercial or lacked the depth required for meaningful

¹ The earliest depictions of sails emerged in the second millennium BC in Egypt, and ship graffiti discovered at *Tarxien* (Fig. 11) are likely subsequent additions from the Bronze Age. However, evidence suggests that maritime movement across the Mediterranean was ongoing during the period of Megalithic construction in Malta, presumably involving the utilization of rudimentary dug-out canoes, such as those unearthed in Bracciano Lake, dating to approximately 5450 BC (Fugazzola Delpino and Mineo 1995; Broodbank 2013). As observed by Broodbank (2013), the diminutive dimensions of these canoes would have necessitated reliance on currents and winds for navigation, substantially influencing their directional capabilities. Nevertheless, the authors argue that despite these constraints, the employment of celestial navigation remains a plausible hypothesis, corroborated by ethnographic evidence from Oceania, where seafaring communities have proficiently navigated considerable distances utilizing celestial guidance.

However, contemporary long-distance swimming achievements between Malta and Sicily underscore the significance of identifying optimal temporal windows—characterized by favorable tides, currents, and meteorological conditions—analogueous to the methods likely employed by ancient mariners utilizing celestial navigation. Within this context, the actual dimensions of the canoes may have been less critical than the capacity to recognize and utilize these advantageous conditions for safe maritime transit.

cultural adoption.

This limited cultural transfer is further emphasized by the contrasting presence of fertility symbols at similar monumental scales between Malta and Sicily. In contrast to the prominent fertility symbols found in Maltese structures such as *Ġgantija*, *Haġar Qim*, and *Tarxien*, Sicily lacks comparable representations at equivalent scales (for reference see Fugazzola Delpino & Tiné, 2002; Cultraro, 2019) (Fig. 12), indicating a distinct divergence in cultural expression between the two regions. This divergence challenges simplistic migration models, suggesting broader cul-

Fig. 12 Evolutionary Schema of Anthropomorphic Statuettes in Neolithic Contexts of Sicily: a simplified evolutionary outline (photo courtesy of Cultraro, 2019)

Fertility cults and the symbolism of Venus statues in ancient Maltese Culture

Malta's unique spiritual evolution is underscored by comparisons with earlier sites such as Göbekli Tepe, which features the first written word for God (circa 9600-9500 BCE) (Seyfzadeh & Schoch, 2019) (Figs. 13 and 14). The Venus figurines of Malta offer a compelling perspective on the evolution of spiritual iconography, potentially signifying the Great Mother Goddess and inviting inquiries into Neolithic divinity. This shift suggests a move from abstract concepts to a possibly matriarchal worldview, necessitating further comparative research into shared iconography and symbolism with cultures, such as Göbekli Tepe. Shared themes of fertility and the sacred in Maltese and Egyptian cultures reveal potential cross-cultural connections, emphasizing the widespread endurance of these beliefs across civilizations. The transition from a more inclusive concept of divinity at Göbekli Tepe to defined gender roles

in later societies, alongside women's prominent roles in cultures such as ancient Egypt, highlights the evolving relationship between gender, power, and religious beliefs throughout history.

Fig. 13 World's First Known Written Word at Göbekli Tepe Means God (photo courtesy of Robert Schoch and Catherine Ulisse, www.robertschoch.com)

Thus, Maltese Venus figurines (Fig. 15) have emerged as key focal points for understanding the evolution of spiritual thought and the persistent influence of feminine symbolism.

The practices of Phoenician colonists (800-700 BC) in Malta and Gadir elucidate the dynamics of cultural interaction, providing a framework for analyzing Maltese megalithic structures¹. The integration of existing megalith structures with Phoenician deities underscores profound engagement with local traditions and supports the argument that these structures functioned as temples

¹ Despite the Phoenician takeover of Malta, the ancient temple sites, especially Tas-Silg, remained visible. This stands in stark contrast to Göbekli Tepe, which seems to have been deliberately covered up and hidden. This key difference in how these sites were treated may indicate contrasting perspectives on spiritual legacy and ritual importance between the two societies. While the concealment of Göbekli Tepe hints at a possible decline in cultural relevance or a change in spiritual customs, the ongoing visibility and use of Malta's temples suggest an enduring cultural and spiritual significance. This reflects how these ancient structures were adapted to fit the changing dynamics of society over time.

at least under Phoenician rule. This contrasts markedly with the absence of dedicated land-based cult evidence for Astarte in Gadir, where maritime worship predominated (Saez Romero, 2021). This disparity indicates strategic adaptations of spiritual practices to local contexts, and questions arise regarding whether prior contacts facilitated the cultural tolerance exhibited by the Phoenicians. Proximity to Tunisia likely facilitated interactions, leading to an exchange of ideas and practices. Although there was a temporal gap, the cultural heritage of the prehistoric inhabitants influenced Phoenician interactions in Malta. This perspective highlights that cultural connections were likely maintained through oral traditions and shared narratives rather than presuming direct relationships between groups.

Fig. 14 Inside *Hagar Qim*, there are narrow passages probably not accessible to the public. Anati (2022) states that the function of these stone tables or mushroom-shaped altars is not clear, however, it is interesting to note the H symbol, which recalls the symbol at Göbekli Tepe (Photo taken by author at *Hagar Qim*)

Fig. 15 Standing female statue; it is hypothesized that the head was fabricated separately, as evidenced by the presence of a socket with dowel holes intended for secure attachment (photo taken from Anati, 2022)

Discussion

Malta: a sacred axis mundi?

Anati (2021) posits a pilgrimage state centered around Malta's megalithic structures, suggesting that these sites served as cultural nexuses within the Mediterranean context. While Bonanno (2021) argues that evidence for this claim is lacking, it raises significant questions: why are these structures concentrated in Malta instead of surrounding regions? The primary conclusion would be that this concentration fulfilled criteria commonly associated with cult areas, including exclusivity, remoteness, and narrative connections. Cult areas often correlate with shared beliefs anchored in known narratives, indicating Malta's significant appeal. For instance, non-locals may have engaged with a shared cosmological framework that transcended localized practices, suggesting that Malta's megaliths acted as gathering points for cultural exchanges and spiritual engagement. Moreover, Malta's geographical positioning is advantageous; it is isolated from Europe and less vulnerable to natural disasters than areas like Sicily, which faced threats from Mount Etna. The celestial alignments of these structures, coupled with the symbols of celestial bodies, reveal an advanced shared understanding of their significance in agriculture, navigation, and culture (Barratt, 2002).

While the navigational role of the Crux constellation remains debated, the presence of star symbolism in artifacts, such as the *Tal-Qadi* stone, indicates significant engagement with celestial phenomena among Malta's ancient inhabitants, prompting questions about their possible roles or connections. Literature often emphasizes alignment as a key factor in structural orientation; however, celestial references may also reflect shared understandings of ritual timing or served as markers for gatherings.

The findings support the notion that local structures functioned as central hubs for social and cultural interaction, with gatherings inspired by cyclical life patterns, similar to contemporary seasonal festivals (Anati, 2022 proposes the market hypothesis). Distinguishing between rituals as

spiritual practices and festivals as broader communal activities that reinforce cultural identity is crucial. Ultimately, whether markets (Anati, 2022) or festivals occurred, the interactions among diverse groups suggest a peaceful and tolerant society.

Key questions emerge regarding the organization of rituals and festivals: who presided over them, and how did they communicate? The convergence of populations at these sites also supports the hypothesis of collaborative construction efforts, which indicates a harmonious and adaptive social structure. This scenario aligns with evidence from communal feasting at sites such as Stonehenge and Durrington Walls (Pearson, 2017; Craig, 2015). If earlier assumptions viewed these societies as primitive and lacking surplus, ongoing research presents alternative perspectives (Anati, 2021; Craig, 2015; Pearson, 2017). Moreover, despite the modest size of temples, deliberate leveling around them suggests intentional designs for hosting groups, challenging the rigid notions of statehood. In this light, any other hypothesis linking construction timeframes or population size warrants reevaluation.

If this hypothesis holds, delineating what constitutes a ritual in this context becomes imperative. Festivals signify unique participation, fostering social connections. Offerings within these spaces, including food and tools, would have symbolized reciprocity between visiting cultures and the local populace. This dynamic enhances our understanding of the society during the megalithic construction period in Malta. However, even Malta would have had distinctive offerings (beyond the celebratory atmosphere, which may have served as a spiritual blessing) such as honey (important for Neolithic farmers, according to Roffett-Salque et al., 2015), medicinal herbs, magic mushrooms (Anati, 2022), and flora (like the sea squill), which could have enriched these communal gatherings. The reciprocal nature of these exchanges suggests why outsiders were drawn to Malta, with its natural resources and sheltered harbors contributing to its appeal. The shared cosmological framework reflected in megalithic structures likely facilitated cultural interactions, as local and visiting commu-

nities celebrated significant hunting and agricultural milestones¹.

In this context, it is crucial to recognize the dynamic nature of population movements and interactions during the Neolithic period, which complicates any attempt to ascertain fixed demographics. Some visitors may have chosen to remain on the island, while others may have returned to their places of origin, making it challenging to precisely quantify population growth or cultural exchange. Nevertheless, the spatial organization of the island's structures reflects its social complexity, indicating that these architectural feats were not mere backdrops to daily life but rather pivotal elements shaping societal organization and cultural identity, not only for the people living on the island, but also for the surrounding regions. The symbols and figurines associated with the structures represent liminal spaces where symbolic and physical journeys converged establishing an "axis mundi" that connected various levels of existence (land, sea and the spirit).

Population dynamics and social complexity

Recognizing the dynamic nature of population movements during the Neolithic is crucial. This complexity complicates efforts to establish fixed demographics, as some visitors may have remained on the island while others returned to their homeland, making the accurate quantification of population growth or cultural exchange challenging. Nonetheless, the spatial organization of the island's structures reflects social complexity, indicating that these architectural feats influenced the societal organization and cultural identity of local inhabitants and the broader region.

The astronomical alignment of these structures played a vital role in determining the timing of rituals and festivities. Solar alignments, closely linked to survival and agricultural cycles, were especially significant. Thus, the solar alignments of megalithic structures can be seen as intentional expressions of the Neolithic understanding of vital cycles. In contrast, stellar alignments may

vital cycles. In contrast, stellar alignments may have been incidental or purposeful based on the context and purpose.

The importance of solar alignment in shaping practical and spiritual practices is significant. Alignments with solstices and equinoxes likely stemmed from an empirical recognition of periods when the Earth received crucial energy from the Sun. For example, the intensity of sunlight around the summer solstice would have been recognized as a time of abundance crucial for agricultural practices. This awareness of solar energy, linked directly to survival, likely elevated the significance of solar alignment in Neolithic society, influencing practical actions such as planting and harvesting, while reflecting deeper spiritual beliefs about the Sun as a life force governing both material and cosmic realms. Stars also served essential navigational functions. The visibility of key stars, besides Crux, likely helped Neolithic peoples in navigating their landscapes or maritime journeys. Beyond practical navigation, stars may have represented a broader acknowledgement of the cosmological forces connecting terrestrial and celestial realms.

By observing celestial patterns, local communities could establish calendars that dictated agricultural cycles and communal celebrations. This structured observance of time aligns with the monumental structures at Göbekli Tepe and Mammoth houses in the Russian steppe, emphasizing humanity's tendency to embed spiritual and communal significance within architecture. Just as the materials from mammoth remains served functional and spiritual purposes, Malta's megaliths celebrated agricultural achievements and the advanced stone-working technologies of Mediterranean cultures.

Contrary to Anati's (2021) assertion that internal features of these structures held greater importance, this analysis contends that external activities and shared experiences surrounding the structures imbued them with meaning. Anati's observation of the global phenomenon of ceremonial urbanization prompts a reflection on the elements that are inherently local to Malta, which may align with broader spiritual or communal traditions.

¹ Akin to contemporary seasonal festivals, for example, in Malta, we celebrate the Imnarja on 29th June traditionally known as the feast for farmers which would take place following the harvest when they would rest after their hard work

Conclusions

Beyond stone: megaliths as milestones in our journey to the foundations of today

This study examined the complex aspects of Neolithic Maltese society, questioning established theories about its roots and evolution. The distinctive megalithic monuments found in Malta have no counterparts in Sicily, despite being suggested as forerunners of the archipelago's inhabitants. This highlighted the importance of comprehending the relationship between southward-to-northward migration and its effects on culture, thus providing valuable perspectives for bridging historical knowledge gaps. This viewpoint helped to clarify certain observations in the current study. For instance, if Crux (Fig. 16) alignment was not crucial for residents, it might have functioned as a navigational aid for outsiders returning to North

Africa (and possibly beyond), where celestial visibility improves further south.

The discussion also evaluated the classification of these structures as temples versus focal buildings, arguing that, while the arrival of the Phoenicians introduced a more defined notion of a temple, earlier constructions may not have represented a significant shift. Notably, the discovery of the term for 'God' at Göbekli Tepe suggests that spiritual thought may have predated the Maltese temple period, yet the Maltese context marked a transition from ethereal concepts to statues representing 'deities'. Future research should concentrate on how earlier traditions, such as those at Göbekli Tepe, might have influenced Neolithic Malta despite their temporal gap, exploring potential evolutionary parallels or similarities.

Fig. 16 Set of holes in the shape of Crux constellation at *Tarxien* (Barratt, 2022) but Anati (2021) argues that they are likely to have been related to some space below them (photo from Anati, 2021, MLT 86 EA II-21)

Furthermore, considering the hypothesis of celebratory practices, this analysis asserts that contrary to the prevalent belief that these builders labored tirelessly, they likely valued their produce, which may have resulted in the legacy of celestial alignments and their connections to rituals and life cycles while incorporating external interactions alongside internal dynamics. Moreover, if Malta functioned as a reference point for surrounding regions, it indicates that the builders possessed skills beyond mere masonry. Cult areas not only share common beliefs and spiritual practices but they are also often grounded in well-documented narratives that enhance their significance, particularly in the absence of a spoken lingua franca. Contrary to dominant scholarly views, this approach suggests that Malta held substantial appeal and tolerance, as non-indigenous individuals were likely attracted to the island not solely for worship but also for participation in a shared cosmological framework that transcended localized practices. The distinctive features of Maltese megalithic culture emerged from a dynamic synthesis of local innovations and broader Mediterranean influences to which other societies possibly related and contributed.

In conclusion, Malta's megalithic structures prompt a reevaluation of contemporary understandings of prehistoric human achievements and challenge assumptions about ancient capabilities and motivations. These builders relied on readily available resources, including stone, flora, and water cisterns. Examining these structures offers critical insights into the sociocultural dynamics shaping human societies, continuously enriching our collective understanding of identity and meaning. Ultimately, they stand as a testament to the enduring quest for creativity and impact, resonating through these monumental legacies and inspiring ongoing scholarship and future research on the multifaceted cultural landscape of the Neolithic Mediterranean.

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